

MOTIVATION IN LANGAUGE LEARNING

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Abstract: Knowledge of a foreign language is now becoming an integral part of the professional competence of a modern specialist of any profile. The desire for practical knowledge of the language is increasing in our time, as the scale of professional mobility is increasing, mass tourism has developed, and the processes of educational migration have intensified. But during the period of study, students usually lack the motivation to learn the language, and the possible prospects for its use in their future professional activities are still unclear to them. The article is aimed to analyze the concept of motivation, its types and made an attempt to identify factors that prevent students from continuing to study on their own foreign language

Key words: motivation, language learning, self-motivation, self-study, integrative motivation, instrumental motivation

Self-study and effective organization of independent work are becoming increasingly important for mastering a foreign language. Without improving the language, students will not be able to develop their language skills outside of the classroom. It was revealed that in order to carry out successful language learning, not only correct and effective organization of one's time is necessary, but also a proactive attitude to search for opportunities for learning a foreign language. Despite the fact that learning a foreign language, especially English, is currently necessary, students are not focused on everyday practice, while classroom study is usually limited to a few hours a week. And as a result, such a study does not provide enough

practice and opportunities for the use of the language, which is unlikely to contribute to the high language level of students.

In the Collins Dictionary, motivation is defined as “The act or an instance of motivating desire to do; interest or drive incentive or inducement (and in terms of psychology), the process that arouses, sustains and regulates human and animal behaviour.” Similarly, the Oxford Dictionary (1993) describes motivation as “A reason or reasons for acting or behaving in a particular way, or desire or willingness to do something or possess enthusiasm.” Gardner (2006) cites that “motivation is a very complex phenomenon with many facets...thus it is not possible to give a simple definition.” Accordingly motivation explains, why people choose a certain activity, how long they are ready go to their goal and what efforts they make to achieve it. There are different types of motivation, such as integrative, instrumental and self-motivation. Integrative motivation is characterized by the desire to master the second foreign language at such a level as to be able to integrate into a society that speaks this language to achieve a certain social positions, get an education, travel and make friends. Integrative motivation consists of three components: integration, attitude to the learning situation and motivation. According to Gardner and Lambert (1959), motivation is identified primarily with the learner's orientation towards the goal of learning a second language. Due to the fact that often the second language is studied in the classroom and students do not have the opportunity communicate with a native speaker, integrative motivation is not developing.

Instrumental motivation is characterized by the desire to master a language with a utilitarian purpose, such as to pass an exam, get a good grade, do not disappoint parents, get an education and a diploma. This kind of motivation is the weakest. But motivation can change over time. Professor Zoltan Dernier from University of Nottingham has developed a model called "system self-motivation L2", which invites the student to imagine themselves as a positive, competent and successful

person who speaks a foreign language. In this model, motivation is considered in dynamics, in stages. The level of students' motivation can rise or fall, depending on interest, involvement in the learning process, on the qualities a learning partner or a classroom teacher. Motivation is influenced by the tasks that the student performs, how interesting they are and absorb the attention of students. According to Zoltan Dornyei, self-motivation learning in a foreign language will be effective if 1) the student is able to build a thoughtful and clear projection of yourself as a successful person, speaking a foreign language, in harmony or, according to at least does not go against the expectations of parents, friends and others elements of society; 2) there is a clear plan of tasks and strategies for learning the language, which will allow, in the end, to achieve the goal, namely to master foreign language.

The biggest problem of the class today is that the teacher has no understanding of effective teaching and motivation. Teachers assume that their students are empty buckets to be filled with knowledge. However, students have total personalities and teachers must understand effective teaching and students' features, otherwise, they will not be successful in teaching. In order to increase students' motivation, the teacher needs to clearly understand the ways and techniques of its formation in the conditions of this university. Spolsky (1990) said that inspired students are more likely to learn faster than those who are not. Important factors influencing the formation of positive motivation learning are the tasks of the lesson, its content and organization. Learning activities should be organized pedagogically and psychologically in such a way that evoke and maintain motivation, experience it and manage it. When the learners are motivated, the teacher could and would discharge their responsibilities in the best way possible (Kondal, 2015). The use of new information technologies in teaching English is considered an effective method as it allow using a wide variety of forms of work and making lessons engaging and memorable for students, for example, tools as Kahoot, Quizlte and Wordwall are applicable in introducing new words or revising

vocabulary. Another example of motivation booster activity is role-playing as it provides ample opportunities to enhance the learning process. Role-playing is a methodological technique that belongs to the group of active methods of teaching practical knowledge of a foreign language. A role-playing game is a conditional reproduction by its participants of real and practical activities, creates conditions for real communication. The effectiveness of training here is primarily due to an explosion of motivation, an increase in interest in the subject.

In conclusion, note that the motivational aspect has an important importance for the activation of all psychological processes - thinking, perception, understanding and assimilation of foreign language material. Motives, areas of interest and inclinations, the student's worldview constitutes a harmonious unity of personality. All this is internal force that encourages the student to learn a foreign language and creates positive attitudes towards learning English. For this, it is necessary increase levels of motivation, contributing to the development of cognition and intellectual activities of students, which, in turn, leads to an increase in the efficiency learning process.

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